

ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING E-COMMERCE SYSTEM

¹*Okpalla, C.L., ²Onyegide, R.U., ³Onyemauche, U.C., ⁴Onyema, C.J., ⁵Nwokoma, F.O., ⁶Chukwuneke, C.I., ⁷Benson-Emenike, M.E., ⁸Onukwugha, C.G.
^{1,2,3,4,5,7,8}Department of Computer Science, Federal University of Technology Owerri,
Nigeria.
⁶ Department of Computer Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This research intends to address some of the problems encountered in the internal process management of e-Commerce system, using StakeXchain as the case study. The expense of developing and sustaining e-Commerce has increased due to the difficulty in managing and analyzing company information from a single source. The lack of flexibility in information transfer from one sector to another and real-time sales consolidation have been encouraged by the use of distinct software for the company's many business divisions. The expense of developing and sustaining e-Commerce has increased due to the difficulty in managing and analyzing company information from a single source. It was important to create a system that could integrate the internal process management of e-Commerce systems in light of all of these preexisting issues. The system created will be able to centralize all business operations, reduce the costs associated with building and maintaining websites, and provide real-time access to vital business data. The Rapid Application Development (RAD) Methodology was utilized to create this Enterprise Resource Planning e-Commerce System, and the following programming languages were employed: Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML5), Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP), Cascading Style Sheet (CSS), JavaScript and jQuery. The cost effectiveness, process visibility and management, enhanced customer relationships, and greater productivity are all taken into account in this research, which is quite beneficial.

Keywords: E-commerce, Real-Time, Cost Reduction, Resource planning

I Introduction

Electronic commerce, or e-Commerce, is quickly becoming a recognized and utilized business model. More and more companies are putting into place websites that offer the ability to conduct business online. It is safe to argue that doing your buying online has become routine. E-Commerce generally refers to purchasing or ordering goods online for a consumer's personal or household use, whether or not the invoice for payment is sent later or the goods are paid for right away using electronic banking, a credit card, electronic payment, or something similar [1]. More small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are joining the global market as a result of the growing convergence of global marketplaces. These SMEs must decide which components of information system adoption and investment will best serve their needs as they participate in the competitive market (local and international). Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, which manage the bulk of system requirements in all functional areas of a corporation including finance, human resources, manufacturing, sales, and marketing, are

integrated, customized, and bundled software-based systems [2]. Through the integration of organizational business operations and the sharing of information between functional areas via a shared database, ERP promises to transmit the best practices built into the technology's architecture itself.

II Research Problems

The handling of data and information flow from one company department to another is inefficient in the present StakeXchain e-Commerce system. For instance, the information generated by the sales department that the inventory department needs is incompatible with the software being used by both departments due to distinct software architectural designs. Information is not centrally located. Additional issues include:

- i inability to organize and analyze company information from a single source.
- ii. Maintaining various software from various company departments is expensive.
- iii. inflexibility in the transfer of knowledge from one industry to another.
- iv. lack of consolidation in sales.

III Significance of the Research

The total operation in terms of sales, customer relationship management, human resources, and inventories will be more streamlined at the conclusion of this research, increasing the pleasure of the StakeXchain workers who work there. A few of the characteristics that the company will gain from after this investigation are as follows:

Firstly, in order for other researchers in the society to conduct this kind of research without difficulty, this research activity will act as a stepping stone for later researchers. Business operations will be able to become more precise, secure, and recorded thanks to this research.

Second, the research will assist in many ways, such as functioning as an Executive Information System (EIS) and Executive Support System, to reduce the stress in managers' decision-making (ESS).

IV Review of Past Work

Organizations started to create applications to maintain inventory, help with material orders, and generate finished things as soon as computers were introduced in the 1960s. Firms made

the first move toward methodically managing the operational part of their business with the idea known as inventory control [3]. Applications for Materials Requirements Planning (MRP) were created in the 1970s to help businesses plan their purchases, estimate demand, and schedule production. As a result, pioneering companies in the sector like SAP and J. D. Edwards were born [4,5]. The main ERP suppliers – SAP, IBM, J. D. Edwards, Baan, PeopleSoft, and Oracle – were formed by the end of the 1980s as organizational executives started to turn to technology to help with everyday operational decision-making [6]. Organizations sought to enterprise applications to differentiate themselves from the competition because they gave decision-makers more visibility into their inventories and production levels.

As the industry became more competitive in the 1990s, the major competitors sought to gain a competitive edge and started to create programs that combined the operational and accounting areas of the company [7]. ERP industry marketing prompted businesses to rush to install these programs as a result of Y2K's dread of the unknown, which resulted in a major increase in ERP providers and services [8,9]. When the dotcom bubble burst in 2001, it shook the whole technology sector, and the big firms in it were under pressure to cut costs [10]. By the end of the 2000s, the ERP landscape had changed due to Oracle's acquisition of J. D. Edwards and PeopleSoft [11] and a newcomer, Infor Global Solutions' acquisition of Baan [12] and IBM's MAPICS product [13]. As a result, SAP, Oracle, and Infor were the top ERP software have advanced as they entered the maturity stage of their lifetime thanks to the sluggish adoption of cloud computing. By relocating all of the hardware needed to support an organization's ERP application off-site to a vendor-hosted site, cloud computing lowers the information technology (IT) overhead for businesses [14].

Problems and Lessons Learned from StakeXchain

The StakeXchain crew became aware of a number of threats to the management of their e-Commerce system. They acknowledged that everyday administrative tasks like data collection and report generation take an inordinate amount of time, that keeping track of customer happiness and inventory levels is getting more difficult, and that maintaining their website is expensive. Because of this, the system has not completely reaped the benefits of e-competitive Commerce's advantage, corporate stability, and profit. This research has looked into the e-Commerce System managed by StakeXchain. The case analysis's findings demonstrate that e-

Commerce and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) integration are necessary for success in the twenty-first century.

The adoption of e-Commerce involves a number of adoption steps [15]. The procedure is drawn out for small and medium-sized organizations (SMEs), while big businesses with plenty of resources and expertise can skip or adopt some stages at once. It is a process whereby an organization progresses from basic to sophisticated e-Commerce, reaching ever-higher degrees of innovation [15]. The business may decide early on to create merely a website to showcase its goods and services. The management may opt in the future to provide opportunities for customers to actively engage, interact, and adapt the information to meet their needs [15]. Enterprises can also benefit from the increased information exchange. For instance, it can better comprehend customer preferences and present suitable products.

Importantly, Brand and Huizingh demonstrated a link between the intention to innovate and adoption level [15]. The need for future innovation is growing along with knowledge and satisfaction levels. Small businesses establish e-commerce through a series of steps in which they steadily expand their electronic capabilities [16].

ERP Systems in Environments of Small and Medium Businesses

Although ERP systems were first created to manage large-scale businesses, SMEs are becoming more and more driven to embrace ERP solutions [17]. A variety of inborn traits that set small and medium businesses apart from large ones include ownership type, organizational structure, cultural traits, and market [18]. Limited finances, limited IS knowledge, and a lack of IT competence are obstacles SMEs in implementation projects must overcome with regard to the issue of IT/IS adoption [19]. Once approved, a SME environment might allocate the whole annual IT budget to ERP installation projects [20]. Due to economies of scale favoring larger businesses, researchers discovered that ERP implementation costs as a percentage of revenue ranged from 0.82 percent for large businesses to 13.65 percent for SME businesses [21]. Compared to large firms, major SME projects have higher internal and external risks. SMEs are less stable externally than large businesses, and therefore have more trouble getting credit [22]. Such external hazards may cause SMEs to postpone or abandon their ERP adoption project altogether. Due to their lack of resources, SMEs may find it challenging to conduct reengineering initiatives internally. Overall, given the limitations outlined above, SMEs may have more difficulty embracing technology than large businesses [22]. Before starting a project of this size, SMEs should be aware of the total cost of ownership of an ERP program given the

hidden costs associated with ERP systems. When deployed effectively, ERP solutions enable a company to acquire a competitive advantage by utilizing resources more efficiently and by quickly adapting to the ever-changing business environment [23]. Additionally, an effectively implemented ERP system can improve employee efficiency, strengthen sales and forecasts, lower inventory turn-around times, and decrease wasteful spending [24]. SMEs believe that an ERP solution will help them stand out from the competition because large businesses have been using them since the mid-1990s, however this notion may be based on a lack of experience and expertise with ERP implementations.

V Limitations from Past works and Importance of this Research.

Several researches have looked at e-Commerce in Small and Medium-sized Businesses (SMEs). However, researches on the integration of e-commerce and enterprise resource planning in SMEs are scarce. It is crucial for both academic scholars and business practitioners to comprehend the characteristics that contribute to automated process management because organizations manage their internal processes on a daily basis.

The contemporary e-Commerce environment is distinctive in some ways. Despite being online, it still uses manual processes for inter-functional data flow and decision-making because business management is decentralized. Because there is different software in each of the company's functional units, this results in an inflexible information flow between those units, raises costs, and makes maintaining the software expensive. Additionally, the method does not consolidate sales. The team management focuses on expanding the business since this issue becomes a roadblock in creating a contemporary and intuitive user experience.

Through the effective integration of the e-Commerce system with enterprise resource planning, this research will be able to address the shortcomings of the current StakeXchain e-Commerce system.

This study also intends to assist StakeXchain in successfully integrating their e-Commerce store with ERP in order to sustain and expand their business by assisting them in finding better ways to manage their internal processes.

VI The Methodology Adopted in this Research

For this research work the methodology adopted is Rapid Application Development (RAD). Rapid Application Development (RAD) is a software development methodology, which involves iterative development and the construction of prototypes.

Reason for Adopting Rapid Application Development Methodology

Businesses today work in a global world that is changing quickly, hence the need for rapid application development. They must react to fresh opportunities and markets, shifting financial conditions, and the appearance of rival goods and services. Since software is used in practically every aspect of corporate operations, it is crucial that new software be built swiftly in order to seize opportunities and adapt to market pressure. Because of this, quick development and delivery is increasingly frequently the most important need for software systems.

Additionally, due to the constantly shifting environment in which these businesses operate, it is frequently very hard to generate an exhaustive list of solid software requirements. Customers find it impossible to forecast how a system will effect working practices, how it will connect with other systems, and what user operations should be automated, therefore the requirements that are proposed invariably change. Time-sensitive small to medium-sized projects benefit the most from RAD.

VII Results

Output Form

Figure1: Administrator's Dashboard

Inventory Report

This Report shows Your Current Stocks States
Inventory Report As At: 16 Aug 2021

Product Name	Qty	Price	Old Price
compact	40	NGN 3500	NGN 4500
Mini Elitebook	32	NGN 4900	NGN 5900
Pavilion Laptop	51	NGN 50000	NGN 60000
Lenovo flat 9600	59	NGN 50000	NGN 60000
EliteBook 6930p	49	NGN 45000	NGN 50000
Accer 6930g	8	NGN 60000	NGN 85000
Expected Revenue	8481800	Total Qty(s) of Goods In-Stock	239

Print Close

Figure 2: Inventory Report

Sales Report

Please Select Date Range of the report to generate
Date range:
07/16/2021 - 08/15/2021

Sales Report As At: 07/16/2021 - 08/15/2021

#OrderID	Product Name	Qty	Price
JZ1450GQ	Pavilion Laptop	1	NGN 50000
DV7394HW	Pavilion Laptop	1	NGN 50000
Net Income	100000	Total Qty(s) of Goods Sold	2

Print Close

Figure 3: Sales Report

Figure 4: Model Diagram of the system

VIII Discussion

The web application includes the following pages and categories:

1. **Home Page:** Is the first page of the application which lead to other pages it contains functions like login, password recovery, contact, shop and about.
2. **Admin Dashboard Page:** Contains user information and also serve as gateway to other modules of the application. This page also shows graphical representation of stock and transactions.
3. **User Payment Page:** Enables the user make his/her payment with most secured and encrypted payment gateway.
4. **Payment Confirmation Page:** All the history of user's transactions is documented here for easy retrieval and accountability purpose.
5. **Settings Page:** Allows the administrator to make modifications on the website and other vital information about the staffs such as password, username for security purpose.
6. **Contact Page:** This is where complaints are written and sent to the customer service.

IX Summary

E-commerce is quickly becoming a recognized and utilized business paradigm. More and more companies are putting into place websites that offer the ability to conduct business online. It is safe to argue that doing your buying online has become routine. More businesses are joining the global market as a result of the growing convergence of global markets. These businesses are compelled to choose investments and adoption strategies for information systems that will meet their needs as they compete in the competitive market (domestic and international). Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems have arguably been identified as one of the most widely used business solutions in recent years, according to studies from numerous information technology academics and practitioners.

X Conclusion

It is clear that a computer is a necessary tool for nearly all facets of a person's everyday activity. This truth cannot be underlined enough on its own. Without a doubt, the use of computers, particularly ERP, in financial processes has made these industries work more efficiently and with less effort. Compared to previous systems, it has also made the information requirements of management and the wider world regarding these industries more accessible.

In the development of computers and software, research and development are ongoing processes. Although this new approach is functional and efficient, there is still opportunity for development. Three-dimensional (3D) e-Commerce application development, or leveraging virtual reality technology to improve customer interaction by delivering shopping experiences with their goods and services akin to in-person purchasing, can further this research. The created ERP E-Commerce system will provide more employment opportunities. StakeXchain's departmental components are all interconnected to produce effective and efficient results.

XI Recommendations

After outlining all that is required for this research to be implemented successfully, the researcher made the following suggestions in an effort to strengthen and address some flaws:

1. People should make use of the new system to prevent having trouble making purchases of goods and services.
2. A virtual reality technology, such as three-dimensional (3D) development, can increase the involvement of customers.

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